

Supercritical fluid and ultrasound-assisted green extraction technologies for catechin recovery

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Abstract

The epimers of catechin include epicatechin, epigallocatechin and epigallocatechin gallate and others. They are important bioactives that have salutary effects, and hence are valuable. For ascertaining biologically-safe and green extraction methods that are non-thermal, this review evaluates the efficiencies of ultrasound assisted extraction (UAE) and supercritical (SC) fluid extraction (with CO₂). Standalone SC-CO₂ could be preferred over UAE, given its selectivity (purer product, no co-extracts) and absence of downstream processing. GRAS solvents as water and ethanol or a hydro-alcoholic mix are preferable for UAE. However, considering the core competency of ultrasound in disrupting cell organelles, a tandem approach with sequential SC extraction is recommended to justify process economics and ensure quality yield of catechin using green technologies.

Keywords: Catechin, Ultrasound, Supercritical fluid, Extraction, Green technology, Non-thermal.

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1 Introduction

Green chemistry has had an immense impact on the science of recovery of valuable bioactives in the modern times, particularly in the last decade. In the field of green analytical chemistry, it has become quite important to consider techniques that are benign on the target bioactives as well as are soft on nature. A rising global consensus on green chemistry-based sustenance in extraction technology has augmented the initiative of making the stakeholders aware of its importance. Particularly, while making a selection of solvents for recovery of active constituents from biological matrices, principles of green chemistry should be adhered to. Several authors have earlier consented to such ideologies [1-3]. Few researchers have also related green engineering as an application of green chemistry, when techniques of engineering that are green have been used in the extraction process [4]. The researchers, in general, find particular interest when these techniques are non-thermal in nature as well.

The non-thermal technology has been a very useful concept in the scientific world, and has garnered more relevance lately than ever before. With an ever increasing threat of global warming, more stress is on utilizing environmentally benign techniques for processing. The practice is therefore favorable, considering the detrimental effects of industrial wastes on the environment otherwise. Green technologies involve lesser to almost no involvement of heat and emission of hazardous effluents. Although care for the environment is important, it is equally important to appraise product quality, as well as process feasibility for the recovery of valued bioactives from a feasibility perspective as well.

The catechin family of flavonoids is quite diverse with epimers such as epicatechin, epicatechin gallate, galocatechin, epigallocatechin and epigallocatechin gallate. Catechins are common in fresh tea leaves, red wine, broad beans, grapes, apricots, and strawberries, to name a few important sources. While epicatechin is abundant in black berries, cherries, apples, pears, raspberry; apple skin typically contains catechin [5]. According to the epidemiological studies, catechins in our diet help to improve immunity, reduce the risks of cardiovascular disorders and certain types of cancer [6, 7]. Reportedly, green tea catechin exhibits inhibitory effects against carcinogenesis of skin, lung, esophagus, stomach, liver, small intestine, colon, bladder, prostate, and mammary glands [8].

Catechins are soluble in polar solvent. Therefore, in order to recover catechin from these natural resources, employment of a polar solvent is convenient. Water could be an economic and

conceivable solvent, at the outset. This disquisition aims to assess the efficiencies of ultrasound assisted extraction (UAE) and supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) for recovery of catechins from natural resources, both of which are quite popular green non-thermal extraction techniques.

2 Why do We Need These Two Techniques?

It is true that a valuable bioactive such as the catechin family is valuable. It is therefore important to consider the appropriate technique to extract them safely from their biological sources. It is also agreeable that green chemistry based techniques should be considered for a safe and sustainable product usage. However, the choice of an appropriate method is tricky, since both methods of recovery are practiced with fine differences. There could be in fact an ambivalence regarding the choice of a reliable technique, and for resolving the puzzle, a comparative assessment is recommended.

Since catechins are valued biomolecules with nutritional and therapeutic benefits, their recovery from natural resources should desirably be convenient and safe. As mentioned, among thermally benign extraction techniques, the present discussion focuses on UAE and SFE technologies. Both these technologies do not involve any hazardous chemical solvents in principle, and the recovered extract is ready for immediate use (or after a minimal processing post-extraction, as for ultrasound).

UAE operates by creating sonic pressure waves, followed by creation of cavitation bubbles, causing implosion and shear due to microturbulence within the sample matrix, thereby disrupting the cellular organelles, and thus resulting in release of the bioactives [9] (Fig. 1). For sample matrices such as tea leaves, UAE has been particularly preferred. Experts in fact favor involving ultrasound probes instead of bath sonicators for higher extraction yield [10]. It is also true that UAE is much practiced in chemical and food sector industries, probably because it is a quick extraction process, and hence, requires comparatively lesser energy than its counterparts in conventional techniques [11]. Though the auxiliary energy needed for UAE is much higher compared to conventional extraction such as maceration, the time and yield of extraction greatly differ between them. Reportedly, for extraction of phenolic compounds from grapes, the time required for UAE was 10 times lesser than that of maceration [12].

But, few authors have expressed concerns about UAE's relatively low efficiency, despite a high exposure time, at least for tea leaves [13]. For catechins however, both extraction time and

temperature have been called critical parameters by the said authors, and therefore, UAE needs to be examined more pragmatically in times to come. As mentioned already, post extraction, there is a brief separation step necessary to recover the extract in original, *per se*, in UAE (since it is recovered from sample matrix in the extracting solvent medium). The extracts are also not selective in nature.

Supercritical (SC) fluids, as is well known, comprise of fluids that in the supercritical state act as a solvent for recovery of biomolecules. SC's have an intermediary behavior between a liquid and a gas. The intermediate behavior works excellently in favor of the fluid in acting as a solvent with an option of fine tuning of solubility. This attribute uniquely offers the selectivity in extracts that is not offered by UAE. CO₂ is the commonest fluid used, and the technology is accordingly called SC-CO₂ extraction. It has been a method of choice owing to its well-known specificity, and near ambient processing that is suitable for thermolabile constituents such as catechins [8, 14]. Also, SC-CO₂ extraction is quick, and the product is ready to use without any further separation/purification step at all, this is another unique feature among extraction methods. On the downside, the technique requires a relatively higher capital investment, more trained manpower and a comparatively high running cost (given there is a cost of accessories of the equipment and CO₂). Fig. 2 shows a detailed view of the SFE system.

The preferences for both these much practiced techniques for obtaining catechin from varied natural sources are multifaceted. They would be evaluated in this article with a view to appraise the advantages and identify the tradeoffs.

3 UAE of Catechin from Natural Sources

Strawberries are a wealth in polyphenols and flavonoids, and they also house catechins. In an attempt, Albuquerque et al. have explored the possibility of recovery of bioactives from *Arbutus unedo*. They worked with variables such as time, temperature and UAE power. They even used ethanol (%) as a variable. UAE produced an yield of 0.71 mg/g dry weight at 314 W UAE power, after 42 min, with 40.3% ethanol [15]. However, these authors have favored maceration and microwave based extraction more, due to higher catechin yield. Since the temperature of the extraction at UAE was controlled below 35°C, this preference could perhaps be owing to better release of the bioactive from the sample matrix. This could further reflect upon the pretreatment nature of maceration and penetrating nature of microwaves. It appears standalone system would

be better off than tandem. This could be an important observation, wherein in future, combination of microwave and UAE could be conceived. Palma and Taylor have considered methanol: water (10:90) mix as extracting solvent with UAE at 30°C for 60 min from grape seeds and obtained 0.65 mg catechin/g dry weight [16]. Curry leaves subjected to UAE with methanol: water (80:20) at 56°C, 145 W, 20 min recounted a yield of 0.48 mg catechin/g dry weight [17].

Cashew leaves when investigated for catechin content have rendered maximum yield of 23% (4946 mg/ kg dry extract) with UAE at 77% amplitude for 31 min, in an ethanolic solvent system [18]. With green tea leaves (*Camellia sinensis* L.), the efficiency of extraction of catechin(s) under optimized UAE conditions of ethanolic solvent (40%), subjected to UAE for 2 h at 40°C has been epicatechin 8.08 mg/g dry weight, epicatechin gallate 8.96 mg/g dry weight, epigallocatechin 9.05 mg/g dry weight and epigallocatechin gallate 61.59 mg/g dry weight, and total catechins at 87.68 mg/g dry weight [19]. A hydro-ethanolic mixture is a feasible solvent system that is both food safe, and efficient. The chemical combinations with other similar food safe solvents could be investigated, to identify any correlation of combinations during direct extraction or a system of pretreatment or maceration prior to UAE.

Effectiveness of hydro-alcoholic solvent (67.81%) system has also been proven for catechin yield from green tea at optimized conditions comprising of 67.81% ethanolic solvent, at 66.5°C for 44 min with a sonotrode operating at 75% amplitude [20]. For walnut leaves catechin hydrate has been recovered at 137.06 mg/100 g dry weight using a hydro-alcoholic solvent system of ethanol 62.82%, UAE for about 49 min, with a liquid: solid ratio of 4.96: 1 [21]. Presence of tannase in sample (such as green tea) has been in contrast to the desirability in extraction, and been attributed to decreased availability of epigallocatechin gallate [22]. This is a striking observation, and should be further investigated since tea leaves have both catechin and tannins. The said authors attempted optimization of antioxidant effect of green tea extract with UAE by extraction of antioxidant-rich fractions. They describe optimized extraction conditions as 44°C, 12 min, tannase concentration 1 mg/mL, and UAE at 360 W in 0.1 M citrate phosphate buffer solvent system. The data reflects that more needs to be addressed with regards to stripping tannins from catechin extracts, as a co-extract.

Catechin by UAE has been reported to provide >90 mg/ g dry sample, when extracted with water as solvent. The researchers claim that power ultrasound (35 kHz) is more potent in extraction of bioactive(s) than sonochemical ultrasound (130 kHz) [23]. This attribute also needs to be

considered in futuristic experimental designs. The said authors have also made use of post conventional UAE for separation of co-extracts from main extract. Although most phenolics take a toll due to post extraction sonication, flavonoids such as catechin are only partially affected. This is a feature that can be worked upon in future for fractionation of co-extracts.

With melissa leaves using water as solvent, at 150 W UAE in 20 min extraction, the yield has been 2.01 mg catechin/g dry weight [24]; whereas from maritime pine at 40°C in 43 min of UAE the yield accrued is 3.5 mg catechin/ g dry weight [25]. For black mulberry leaves, yield of catechin by water assisted UAE has been 11.70 mg catechin/g dry weight, which is more than the conventional extract with hot water decoction. The operating conditions in UAE has been low and also requires lesser solvent [26]. The data provides reasonable evidence in favor of water for catechin extraction by UAE.

Catechin yield of 87.18 µg/ g dry weight, protocatechuic acid (10.63 µg/g dry weight) and epicatechin (9.78 µg/ g dry weight) have been obtained by Ismail et al. using UAE. They recommended optimized conditions of 60°C, 30% amplitude, 20 min and 30 mL/g solvent (methanol: water: HCl = 80:19:1 v/v/v) to solid ratio have been recommended for baobab (*Adansonia digitata*) [27]. These authors further observed that temperature of extraction, and the solvent: feed ratio have significant impact on the yield of total flavonoids (including catechins). They actually used combination of three solvents so as to recover more bioactives. The inclusion of HCl is intriguing and could be perceived as the cause of cell disruption without physical agitation, improvising the acid's mild corrosive nature. For robust plant materials with a tough cell wall, such initiatives should provide quicker availability of bioactives at the cellular surface. They aid in softening the tissues so that shear forces of unit operations subsequently are better able to make the bioactives available to the extracting solvent, more conveniently.

In a separate endeavor, Singh et al. published their find on the extraction performance of UAE in mung beans for catechin (as a part of total flavonoids). They established a recovery hierarchy, bean's part wise, i.e, hull> whole >cotyledon [28]. Among the solvents tested, maximum catechin recovery observed has been in the order of their efficiencies, acetone>ethanol>methanol>water. In another study on mung bean, a yield of 1.91 g/kg has been obtained at the optimized extraction conditions of 37.6% ethanol, 1:35 solid: solvent ratio, 46 min, 500 W ultrasound power at 70°C [29]. Efficiency of acetone is interesting, and could be attributed to polarity.

The UAE process offers quick recovery with comparatively simpler technology. But a potential risk of UAE could be prolonged heat or unregulated shock waves on the vegetative cells, We do require the preferred bioactive, but of course not the unnecessary biomass attached. Soft tissues in certain agro-commodities could be fragile enough to detach from the main biomass under UAE exposure and mix in the solvent with the desired bioactive. That would entail a separate, dedicated and plausibly an extensive downstream processing. It appears that hydro-alcoholic pre-treatment should provide some respite, both pre-process and during the process, making the unit operation brief, and at low energy. Energy based discussion are also encouraged to reflect upon the endurance of various biological matrices exposed to UAE. Such a data sheet should act as a control measure and guide for UAE process optimization and cost-effectiveness.

3.1 Kinetics and Degradation of Catechin

The kinetics of extraction of catechin by UAE is an important aspect that every researcher should study since it is a thermolabile compound, and UAE is known to generate heat during treatment. However, there are a few studies that portray this kinetics. In the work of Albuquerque et al. discussed earlier in section 3, the researchers obtained a second order polynomial equation to model the UAE (Eq. 1) [15]. Also, there was no significant effect observed for the interaction between the process parameters, t (time), P (power), and S/L (content of ethanol) on the yield of catechin (Y).

$$Y = 0.69 + 0.02t + 0.02P - \frac{0.8S}{L} - 0.02t^2 - 0.03P^2 - 0.13S/L^2 \quad (1)$$

Effect of time and temperature of extraction and power of ultrasound has been studied by researchers for aqueous extraction of catechin and gallic acid from *Syzygium cumini* seed kernel powder [30]. Though the authors have not studied the kinetics model of the extraction, they have optimized the extraction of catechin individually at 12 min, 35°C, 125 W with 60% duty cycle (i.e. 1.2 min 'ON' and 0.8 min 'OFF', per cycle). The yield of catechin at this optimized condition was 2.2 mg/g of raw material. Fig. 3 exhibits individual effect of the process parameters on the yield of catechin and gallic acid. However, a thorough study on the combined effects of all these parameters is still warranted.

The major concern of catechin extraction by UAE, which is also responsible for the low yield of catechin is the heat produced during the extraction. Apart from that, the free radicals generated

by the high intensity ultrasound waves also can oxidize sensitive molecules such as catechin. A study on the stability of catechin under a wide range of frequency and power of ultrasound, as well as different temperatures, conducted by Zhu et al. exhibited first order kinetics of degradation of catechin during UAE [31]. The study showed the degradation of catechin increased by almost 17% with increased ultrasound frequency from 28 to 135 kHz; whereas, an increment in ultrasound power from 0.05 to 0.45 W/cm² increased the degradation by 11% owing to the rapid formation of cavitation bubbles. Moreover, rise in temperature (from 30 to 70°C) caused severe degradation of catechin at any frequency of ultrasound, especially at 135 kHz (degradation ratio 77%). Therefore, for enhanced yield of catechin by UAE from any matrix, a lower frequency along with a lower ultrasound power is preferable although that will increase the time of extraction at a greater level. In this context, the kinetics model deduced from the above study would be useful to estimate the variance of concentration of catechin at any point of ultrasound treatment (Eq. 2).

$$C = C_0 \exp \left[-128.8 t f^{0.0355} \exp \left(-\frac{30045.15 f^{-0.032}}{RT} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

where, C represents the concentration of catechin after ultrasonic treatment (mg/mL), t is treatment time (min), C₀ represents the initial concentration of catechin (mg/mL), f is the ultrasonic frequency (Hz), R is the gas constant (8.3145 J/mol/K), and T is the temperature (K).

4 Extraction of Catechin by SFE

Catechin yield extracted from betel nuts (ground to d_p of 177 μm) by SC-CO₂ has been at 565 ppm (mg/kg) (analyzed by HPLC) at optimized conditions of 70°C, 30 MPa, 5% methanol as modifier, and a flow rate of 4 mL/min of CO₂ [32]. In another study, extraction of catechin from peanut skin by SC-CO₂ yielded 208.73 μg/g catechin (HPLC analysis) at the extraction conditions of 70°C, 30 MPa, 180 min, 5% co-solvent (ethanol), flow rate 3 mL/min for CO₂. The said authors compared the performance of ethanol, water and *n*-hexane under conventional techniques, and revealed that catechin was most soluble in ethanol > water > *n*-hexane. In fact, the *n*-hexane fraction did not have any catechin content owing to the polar nature of catechin [33]. Indeed, the partial polarity of ethanol is useful over pure polarity of water, and the purely non-polar hexane fraction is hence devoid of any catechin content. In this regard it is worth mentioning that since polarity of SC-CO₂ varies with operating conditions, the catechin yield could be best optimized with SFE, given its selectivity.

With *Cratoxylum prunifolium*, Cao et al. have achieved 1 mg/g of epicatechin gallate and epigallocatechin gallate in SC-CO₂ extraction at 40°C, 25 MPa, 80% ethanol as modifier [34]. Green tea has been long known to be a rich source of catechins. With green tea, catechin content has been optimized under SFE at 60°C, 25 MPa, 3 h extraction time, 0.5 mL/min flow rate of modifier (ethanol). The process produced an extract yield of 2.9 g from 10 g sample having 2.77% (g/100 g) catechin, ascertained by HPLC-DAD by Sökmen et al. The catechin(s) thus recovered however consisted of epimers of catechin comprising of catechin (0.01%), epicatechin (1.16%), epigallocatechin (0.1%) and epigallocatechin gallate (0.48%). These authors have specifically excluded co-extraction of caffeine from green tea, by adopting sequential extraction. Under this scheme, the authors first stripped the green tea sample from caffeine at specific conditions, followed by extraction of catechin with the same feed and same extraction conditions with modifier [35]. This is quite a remarkable method to avoid co-extraction.

Similar sequential extraction has been conducted by Serdar et al. wherein optimized separation conditions were 60°C, 250 MPa, 180 min, ethanol as modifier at 0.5 mL/min flow rate from Turkish green tea sample. The total run time was 3 h for caffeine and 3 h for catechin, i.e. in total 6 h for complete catechin extraction, per double run (direct method) [36]. These authors however contemplated using microwave treatment first, since it is way briefer than SC-CO₂ in process time, and the mixed yield could be separated post extraction by SFE. This would vastly save on time, and provide more yield. The researchers first isolated caffeine then catechin. They have even used the same feed thrice for repeated extractions, to recover the maximum bioactive yield. Dried, fresh and frozen green tea leaves have been reportedly employed in the said study, with sample-based yields in hierarchy of dried leaves>frozen leaves> fresh leaves, with cycle-based yield hierarchy being first cycle>second cycle>third cycle. A pretreatment with microwave has provided a better yield, as observed by the said authors. Under second scheme (sequential), 4 min microwave treatment followed by 3 h SFE sufficed for extraction of catechin(s), comprising of epigallocatechin, catechin, epicatechin, epigallocatechin gallate (in the order of detection by HPLC). In green tea samples worked upon, catechins were present in the order of amount as epigallocatechin>epigallocatechin gallate>epicatechin>catechin. Among 10, 20, 25 and 30 MPa tested, 25 MPa provided highest yield [36]. This indicates that regulated pressure plays a role in extraction efficiency, and not only a ramp. Also, pretreatment (solvent/process) becomes highly recommended for achieving a better yield.

With fresh frozen green tea leaves, 4.2% (w/w) (848.09 mg epigallocatechin gallate/g sample, 3.60 mg epicatechin/g sample) has been recovered by Gadkari et al. at 50°C, 35 MPa, liquid: solid = 200:1. Considering extraction of catechin also, slightly different conditions of extraction have been recorded at 50°C, 25 MPa (rest parameters same). The second set produced 722.68 mg epigallocatechin gallate/g sample and 18.3 mg catechin/g sample. The SC-CO₂ extract yield of catechin has been assessed by the said researchers to be 15 times more than that by conventional solvent extraction (Soxtec). Importantly, due to selective extraction phenomenon of SC-CO₂, caffeine co-extraction was avoided [37]. Though previously discussed in section 3.1, it is worth mentioning here that owing to the thermolabile nature of catechin, the temperature of SFE for catechin extraction becomes a vital process parameter that needs extra sensitivity during optimization. Since most of the extractions were conducted at high temperatures (50-70°C), there lies a possibility of degradation of catechin in greater extent during extraction itself. This demands further study on degradation of catechin in supercritical conditions.

Since there is no study reported on the kinetics of catechin extraction by SFE, an overview of the kinetics of extraction of total polyphenols can be considered. In a study of polyphenol extraction from lees obtained from pisco-making by SC-CO₂ with ethanol as modifier, the researchers reported the optimum conditions at 200 bar, 40°C [38]. The kinetics of extraction was represented by a spline which contained constant extraction rate (CER) period, falling extraction rate (FER) period and diffusion-controlled (DC) period (Fig. 4). From this curve, the duration of CER clearly indicated the minimum time needed for the extraction for a SFE batch at a particular condition (t_{CER}); such as, for 200 bar, at 0.9 h, the rate of extraction was the highest. At this time, the relative yield of extract (R_{CER}) was equivalent to 37% of the global yield which reduced to 18% at 350 bar. The mass transfer rate was also highest at this condition. Similar investigation is crucial for catechin extraction to observe the rate of recovery of the molecule from its matrix in SFE.

When contemplating the choice of modifier for catechin extraction by SC-CO₂, Bermejo et al. provide the data for the decision. They tested commonly employed modifiers in food systems in their study with SC-CO₂ [39]. Their data reflects catechin yields at ethanol (6.7 mg/g tea leaves) > ethyl lactate (0.8 mg/g tea leaves) > ethyl acetate (0.2 mg/g tea leaves). The operating conditions of SC-CO₂ extraction were 70°C, 30 MPa, 240 min (including 30 min of pre-CO₂ static period). Hence, ethanol yet again proves its suitability as a choice of modifier in extraction.

5 Combined UAE and SC-CO₂ Extraction

While working with spruce bark (a source of phenolic compounds and catechin), few authors have made a comparative evaluation of extracts obtained by SC-CO₂ and UAE. At the operating conditions of 40°C, 8.27 MPa (1200 psi), 60 min, SC-CO₂ produced a significantly higher yield of catechin (171.17 mg/L or ppm) than UAE that was operated at 40°C, 60 min (112.08 mg/L or ppm), as ascertained by HPLC analysis of the extracts [40]. The said authors have claimed that total polyphenols obtained by SFE was 3.65 times higher than UAE; whereas, total phenols in SFE were 1.82 times higher, despite the former being more selective in recovery of bioactives. Notably, the process conditions were similar in both cases, and the find justifies SC-CO₂ as a preferred choice for catechins from spruce bark. With similar plant matrices, alike extraction performance could be expected by SC-CO₂.

Catechin from grape pomace being considered as proanthocyanidins have also been higher on SFE (810.5 mg catechin/100 g dry matter) vs. UAE (70.1 mg catechin/100 g dry matter) [41]. Moreover, the authors involved report that SFE was 10 times more capable in recovery of monomeric fractions than UAE, attesting higher selectivity of SFE that could be made best use of for nutritional gains. However, the same authors favor a tandem of UAE and SFE of the UAE- raffinate for improving the recovery of catechins, even more (62%) than SFE alone. This could perhaps be owing to opening of more cellular pores by UAE allowing better SFE performance.

Moreover, the high temperature required for both UAE and SFE needed to be compromised for higher recovery of catechin. All these aspects necessitate the use of UAE prior or along with SFE to enhance the mass transfer of catechin by rupturing the cell wall of the matrix at lower temperature with the help of cavitation generated by a short pulse of power ultrasonication. A typical UAE-SFE system consists of an ultrasound transducer and a power generator/controller along with the SFE unit. Fig. 5a depicts a SFE extractor along with the ultrasound transducer. The transducer can be cylindrical or multiplate (Fig. 5b). According to Santos-Zea et al., the effect of SFE with multiplate transducer is higher compared to only SFE to obtain an extract with almost 3-folds higher yield of phytochemicals [42]. Riera et al. have also reported 20% enhancement of yield of oil from almond by UAE-SFE. This suggests the need of study of the combinatorial effect of UAE and SFE on extraction of catechin that in turn can reduce the need of temperature for extraction [43].

The utilization of UAE along with SFE is more prominent for the extraction of gingerols from ginger; the researchers obtained field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) images of the ginger particles post-extraction that prove the damages of cell wall caused by UAE that facilitated the extraction (Fig. 6) [44]. The authors also deduced that the enhancement of effective diffusivity by UAE is the reason for higher mass transfer during the extraction process.

6 Outlook on the Most Feasible Extraction Plan of Catechins

Table 1 summarizes the comparison of UAE and SFE for extraction of catechin. Based on the findings and data discussion, it is clear that catechin have co-extracts, typically caffeine, tannin etc. that are naturally present together. The downstream processing should also be minimized for higher throughput in a pilot plant or large scale production. Given the fact that UAE is effective in creating pores for easy access of solvents to solubilize catechin, a selective solvent in such system appears to be more desirable, and a polar solvent would be more appropriate. Although UAE has been much success with even water being used, lack of selectivity is the main hurdle. Recovery of the concentrated extract from water is another challenge, due to low volatility of water compared to commonly used solvents, hence it requires cumbersome evaporation. It is known that SC-CO₂ is selective, and therefore, is specific, and additionally is devoid of post extraction processing requirement.

Assuming batch processing, it is fair to conceive that SC-CO₂ would be more convenient in a large scale setup. If one can recycle the CO₂ emitting, then recurring costs could also be curtailed to a larger extent. In fact, the tandem concept of UAE (power ultrasound instead of bath sonication) and SC-CO₂, that too sequential SC-CO₂ should be the choice, as per the available literature. The green solvent of ethanol has been time and again proven to be suitable as a modifier, and that should be fine for SC-CO₂ extraction. A hydro-ethanolic mix could be worked out to further economize the process, maintaining efficiency of UAE.

Another aspect that could be explored is the effect of particle size, and ethanolic pretreatment before UAE. Drying fresh samples, typically for moist samples such as green tea leaves is also a prerequisite. Among many techniques available for drying, more research is recommended to explore the impact of such methods, since each process contributes to the yield. Although the array of equipments for recovery could add up in cost, a better and specific yield could be a well-earned

dividend. Of course, this would also minimize any tradeoffs and justify more pragmatic gains than implied.

6.1 Combined Extraction by UAE and SC-CO₂

Importantly, the combined approach would circumvent the difficulty of recovery of catechins from within the source; with the benefits of both the techniques, would minimize the thermal degradation of catechin, and avoid hazardous chemical pre-treatment (that would have otherwise been necessary for good recovery). However, future authors are urged to work out combinations of effect of other food-safe green solvents on the extraction performance also. Effectiveness of ethanol as solvent for UAE or as modifier in SC-CO₂ and the combined UAE- SC-CO₂ process reveals the usefulness of its partial polar nature, and the consequent influence of the said solvent on extraction efficiency. A food safe solvent system as ethanol also provides a means for non-hazardous and hassle free usage. Combination of ethanol with other food safe solvent systems could be also envisaged. Pretreatment of samples with hydro-ethanol along with array of extractions is also suggested. Another avenue that needs to be worked upon is the comparison of UAE vs. SFE based on energy consumption for extraction processes, preferably considering yield of bioactive per unit biomass per unit energy. Standalone reporting would also be useful for either processes for designing efficient extraction equipment and scale up activities. That would appraise the process feasibility in greater detail.

7 Conclusion

For recovery of catechin from natural resources, evaluating various parameters and reported literature, it is fair to conclude that wherever possible sequential UAE and SC-CO₂ extractions should be practiced. The desirability of extracts for commercial use is minimum to no co-extracts ideally that warrants use of a selective behavior solvent system. Also, sufficient yield is prerequisite that is provided by a process such as UAE. Role of ethanolic or hydro-ethanolic solvent systems for UAE, and ethanol as modifier in SC-CO₂ is also important. The thrust should be more on GRAS status solvents that include water and ethanol for UAE. Even a hydro-alcoholic mix could be conceived for UAE followed by SC-CO₂. The exposition thus concludes that although SC-CO₂ alone is a better alternative, a tandem approach of using both can provide an overall higher and a purer catechin yield. Such catechin-rich extract would be instantly ready for

direct food applications. Care for the environment also needs to be paid attention to. In fact, by employing green chemistry based techniques for extraction of valuable bioactives (as catechins), we are not only making the end product safe, but also making a significant contribution in rendering the planet free from toxicants and recalcitrant substances. Indeed, applied principles of green chemistry combined with non-thermal technology should be the way forward.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Symbols used

d_p Average particle diameter

Abbreviations

UAE	Ultrasound Assisted Extraction
SC	Supercritical
SFE	Supercritical Fluid Extraction
SC-CO ₂	Supercritical Carbon dioxide
HPLC	High Performance Liquid Chromatography
DAD	Diode-array Detector
CER	Constant Extraction Rate
FER	Falling Extraction Rate
DC	Diffusion-controlled
FESEM	Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy
GRAS	Generally Recognized as Safe

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Figure

Figure 1. Setup of ultrasound-assisted extraction device [45].

Figure 2. Supercritical fluid extraction system [45].

Figure 3. Yield of catechin and gallic acid from *Syzygium cumini* seed kernel powder based on the UAE process parameters (a) time, (b) temperature, and (c) power of ultrasound [30].

Figure 4. Overall extraction curve of polyphenols from lees of pisco-making, at 200 bar, 40°C, with $12.6 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-5}$ kg (CO₂ + ethanol)/s [38].

Figure 5. (a) Schematic of extractor used for UAE-SFE [43] (b) Ultrasound transducers used for UAE-SFE, (i) cylindrical, (ii) multiplate [42].

Figure 6. FESEM images of ginger particles post-extraction (A) without ultrasound, (B) with ultrasound [44].

Table 1. Comparison of ultrasound assisted extraction and supercritical extraction techniques for catechin recovery from different substrates.

Source of catechin	Ultrasound assisted extraction					Supercritical fluid extraction					References
	Solvent	Temperature (°C)	Power/frequency	Time (min)	Catechin content	Solvent	Temperature (°C)	Pressure	Time (min)	Catechin content	
Spruce (Picea abies) bark	Ethanol/water mixture (70%), biomass/solvent ratio of 1:10 w/v	40	35 kHz, 320 W	60	112.08 mg/L of solvent	CO ₂ and ethanol (70%) as co-solvent with 10:1 mL/min flow rate ratio	40	8.3 MPa	60	171.18 mg/L of extract	[40]
Ground grape marc	Ethanol as extracting solvent	80	20 kHz, 80 W	4	Total polyphenols of 2336 mg/100 DM of GAE	6 kg/h CO ₂ modified with 10% ethanol-water solution	40	8 MPa	-	Total polyphenols of from UAE raffinates 2736 mg/100 DM of GAE	[41]
Strawberry fruits (<i>Arbutus unedo</i> L)	Ethanol concentration 40.3 %	30-35	100-400 W	45	0.71 mg/g dry weight of catechin	Ethanol up to 20% as co-solvent	48	6 MPa	60	25.72 mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE) total phenols/g extract	[15, 46]
Apple pomace	Ethanol 50%	20-37	24 kHz, 150 W	30	Total phenolics of about 850 mg/100 g dry matter	Ethanol up to 5% as modifier	55	30 MPa	120	Total phenolics of 5.8 % w/w of freeze dried sample	[47, 48]

Black mulberry leaves (<i>Morus nigra</i> L.)	Water	55	49 W/cm ²	15	Catechin of 0.021 mg/g dry weight	CO ₂ at 0.194 kg/h flowrate	23	1.5 MPa	-	Catechin of 0.84 mg/g of extract	[26] [49]
Green tea	40% ethanol	40	-	120	Caffeine and total catechins of 87 mg/g dry weight	Ethanol modifier at 0.5 mL/min. flow rate	60	25 MPa	180	2.90 % in 10 g dry sample	[19] [50]
Betel nuts	Soaked in 70% (v/v) ethanol	58	40 kHz, 300W	42	Total phenol was 164.74 mg catechin equivalents /g of betel nut seed	5% (v/v) methanol as modifier	70	30 MPa	60	34.00 mg extract/g sample	[32, 51]
Peanut skin	-	50	240 W	9	5.93% of polyphenols	5% concentration of ethanol as co-solvent	70	30 MPa	120	208.73 µg/g sample	[33] [52]

